

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

Study on the Process and Properties of Carbon Nanotube Film Curing Carbon Fiber Composites

Zhiwei Liu¹, Yan Zhao¹, Xiangbao Chen^{1*}

¹School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China

Introduction

- Carbon nanotubes is a one-dimensional nanomaterial. In the structure of carbon nanotubes, carbon atoms are dominated by chemical bonds formed by sp^2 hybridization, and p orbitals overlap each other outside the graphene sheets of carbon nanotubes to form highly delocalized large pi bonds. The special internal structure of carbon nanotubes brings higher mechanical strength, more excellent electrical and thermal conductivity than graphite.
- In this paper, a series of carbon nanotube films with different thicknesses were prepared by vacuum suction filtration method. Based on this, the electrothermal performance of carbon nanotube films with different thickness under electrification conditions was investigated, and the appropriate carbon nanotube films for curing carbon fibers were selected. The composite material cured, and was compared with the traditional oven fixed-line process in terms of power consumption, temperature response time, curing degree and mechanical properties of the parts, and the feasibility and process advantages of the composite were verified. Finally, the prospects for the future research and development of this new curing process are presented.

Introduction

Morphology of carbon nanotube films

The thickness of the carbon nanotube film was uniform and the surface was smooth without obvious defects. Under sem, the bonding between carbon nanotubes is dense, which is easy to form a good conductive path. In addition, the bonding and entanglement between carbon nanotubes can effectively improve the electron transmission efficiency, and thus have a favorable impact on its thermal conductivity.

The macroscopic morphology of the carbon nanotube thin film (extracted and filtered from 100mL carbon nanotube dispersion)

Scanning electron micrograph of carbon nanotube thin film (JSM 7500, 2000×)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electrothermal properties of carbon nanotube films

Voltage was applied to the carbon nanotube film, and the electrothermal heating performance was tested. It was found that with the increase of temperature, the resistance of the carbon nanotube film gradually decreased, and the surface temperature gradually increased. The test on the uniformity of surface temperature of the film also showed that the film had good heat uniformity. As the thickness of CNT film increases, the surface heating temperature increases. The large amount of contact resistance generated by the complex microstructure inside the carbon nanotube film has a crucial influence on this process.

For the small size carbon fiber reinforced composites (70mm 70mm) prepared at present, the curing process of carbon nanotube film has no air medium hindrance, so the temperature hysteresis effect is greatly reduced, and the energy consumption is correspondingly reduced (only 15W) .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

Thank You!